

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

Megacity crime management strategies on human security: Evidence of target hardening and developmental prevention in Lagos state, Nigeria

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World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2022, 16(01), 717–726

Publication history: Received on 17 September 2022; revised on 16 October 2022; accepted on 19 October 2022

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2022.16.1.1070>

Abstract

Lagos, a port and land border megacity, is assailed by waves of violent crimes, alarming traffic blight, unresponsive Federal system of government as been under policed in the face of leap bounding population. How the State has found her own security expression voice independent of the newly created regional Amotekun Security Network is attracting academic attention. It was against this background that this study engaged participatory Theory to analyse megacity crime management strategies on human security in Lagos state, Nigeria. The study employs target hardening and developmental prevention security approaches to measure crime management strategies as it relates to human security. This study adopts qualitative research design using content analysis of publicly available archived documents with reliance on secondary data. The research is conducted by reviewing literature pertaining to crime management strategies, violent crime and its effects on human security in a megacity setting. The literature was obtained through searches in publicly available material. Literature from non-serial publications, official reports, and conferences has been included particularly if they have been cited by other references in term crime management strategies. Results that emanate from this study revealed target hardening positively correlate with provision of human security, while result also shows a disconnect between the State's developmental prevention strategy and human security. This study also submits that prevalence of violent crimes in Lagos state is as fallout of poor crime management strategies. The study recommends that Lagos state government should invest more into target hardening towards achieving a safer city while the Federal Government should also give a support as a safer Lagos translates to confidence of foreign investors in the country. The study also recommends that Lagos state government should engage more NGOs in evolving a stronger developmental protection strategy, deeply inculcated in both formal and informal educational system in order to stems traces of crime and criminalities at tender ages.

Keywords: Developmental Prevention Strategy; Human Security; Participatory Theory; Target Hardening Strategy

1. Introduction

Crime and violence crimes are Siamese twins to urbanisation world over particularly, megacities and such is not limited to developing nations. The responsiveness of governance to prevent and control the monstrous surge in crime and criminality is what thus sends signals of safety to potential investors or otherwise. Crime management could be both short and long term focused and deployed simultaneously to make crimes unattractive and of a lesser gains while also working with long term focus to correct behavioural tendencies that facilitate criminal tendencies (Achumba *et al.*, 2013). Environmental target hardening and developmental prevention strategies are essential components of crime management strategies as seen evolving in Lagos State, Nigeria.

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Lagos State is the current economic fulcrum of Nigeria, already tagged as the eighth fastest growing city in Africa and a window to the future due to her population above the threshold of 10million, a population density above 2000 inhabitants per square kilometer, a large surface footprint of urban towns, and an extensive transportation system. While Tokyo (Japan) is currently the largest 'megacity' in the world with 37.4 million inhabitants, it is estimated that in 2100 it will be Lagos (Nigeria) with 88 million (Iberdrola, 2021: World Population Review, 2017) and is said to increase by 85 people an hour (World Economic Forum, 2016). Urbanisation which comes with tremendous economic opportunities also has its downsides which could be overwhelming particularly for developing countries with weak institutions to address evolving downsides.

Predictably, the urbanisation stride of Lagos state has produced ample negative externalities; rising social inequality with around two-thirds of Lagosians live in slums, growth in waves of violent crimes of kidnapping, highway banditry, land grabbing, drug cartels, maritime piracy, traffic banditry and an alarming traffic blight described as the 'worst in the world' (Business Insider, 2016). It is amidst these confounding urbanisation downsides, that Lagos state, under a federal political system, in sharp contrast to many of its megacity counterparts elsewhere on the continent, embarked on series of reforms that have enabled it to better manage the process of urbanization towards a smart city status; the BRT bus services, highest Internally Generated Revenue (IGR), ongoing electric train projects, Smart vehicle plate detection system, Lagos State Security Trust Fund, deployment of massive CCTV, creation of Lagos State Neighbourhood Security System (LSNC), Lagos State Transport Management Agencies (LASMA) and the deployment of crime management strategies, all these could possibly have occasioned some public analyst to hail Lagos as 'a model city' (Kaplan, 2014).

Environmental target hardening entails environmental development, design through territoriality, surveillance strategy, security barriers, street lighting, including the deployment of closed circuit television camera (CCTV) and engagement of body worn camera. This strategy does not only remove the attractiveness of crime and limited the opportunity but also harden up the environment from crime and criminality. The deployment of techno driven security strategy could be seen in scaling up security provision particularly in addressing the problem of lack of manpower which resulted in Lagos State as an under policed State. Developmental prevention strategy is of long term consequences as it is an intervention concept designed to prevent the development of criminal potential in individuals, particularly those targeting risk and protective factors discovered in studies of human development (Farrington & Welsh, 2007). These crime management strategies does not only recognize that crime is occurring and experienced at the local level, but it equally signifies the emergence of a micro crime policing strategy and of importance to achieve the desired human security which places human safety at the centre of security.

Interestingly, since Security is under the exclusive list of the Federal government and Lagos is short staffed in security manpower, commitment of Lagos state to crime management in bridging this gap could be seen in not only in setting up different paramilitary outfits to care for pitfalls of an emerging megacity; Lagos State Traffic Management Authority (LASTMA) for traffic management, Lagos Neighborhood Safety Corps (LNSC), a Community Oriented Policing meant to feed federal security agencies with information to secure lives and properties, Lagos Environmental Sanitation Corps (LAGESC) to care for waste management, a Law Enforcement Training Institute, (LETI) in 2013 to set standards for recruitment of law enforcement agents, training, and development of the officers all geared towards. The State cater for federal security services and her own created agencies through a well structured Lagos State Security Trust Fund, which encourages corporate bodies to be involved in joint funding for security of Lagos state.

To achieve the objective of this study, answers are provided to the below research questions;

- To what extent does environmental target hardening strategy affects human security in Lagos State, Nigeria?
- How does developmental prevention strategy influence human security in Lagos State, Nigeria?

2. Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Human Security

The UN General Assembly's (2012) resolution 66/290 defines human security as an approach to assist Member States in recognizing and addressing widespread and cross-cutting challenges to the survival, livelihood and dignity of their people. It calls for "people-centred, comprehensive, context-specific and prevention-oriented. The concept of human security is vital in building the resilience of civilian populations, not only in fragile States but world over, working towards the advancement of security before, during and after a crisis and building stability and peace (United Nation Human Security Unit, 2014). Proponents of human security actually contest the traditional concept of national

security through military security by asserting that the appropriate referent for security should be at the human level rather than national level.

Therefore human security is a people-focused and multi-disciplinary understanding of security which involves ensuring the presence of Economic security, Food security, Health security, Environmental security, Personal security, Community security and Political security. In a mega city like Lagos State, every pillar of human security could be seen under threat with prevalence of crimes and violent crimes on the highway, in the neighbourhood, fear of kidnapping or traffic bandits, cult clashes, rapes, land grabbers and area boys. Human security is a flexible approach and can be tailored to different contexts as threats to human security can exist at all levels of development. They can emerge slowly and silently or appear suddenly and dramatically.

2.1.2 Target Hardening Strategy

Target Hardening Strategy also known as situational crime prevention is a preventive crime management concept that relies, not upon improving society or its institutions, but simply upon reducing opportunities for crime. Crime opportunistic reduction is achieved essentially through some modification and reinforcement of the physical environment, products, or systems in order to directly affect offenders' perceptions of increased risks and effort and decreased rewards, provocations, and excuses (Cornish & Clarke 2003). Target Hardening aligns that crime is not randomly distributed across a city or community but is, instead, highly concentrated at certain places known as crime "hot spots" (Sherman *et al.* 1989).

In Lagos, the increase in traffic robbery is quite unsettling and alarming resulting in loss of lives and dispossession of properties (Usman, 2021). Situational crime prevention often raises concerns over the displacement of crime. This is the notion that offenders simply move around the corner or resort to different methods to commit crimes once a crime-prevention project has been introduced, this is also known as crime displacement. Naturally in areas where CCTV are deployed or officers of LSNC situated for foot and bike patrol, crime rates will naturally thinned out (Daniel, 2021).

2.1.3 Developmental Prevention Strategy

The developmental perspective posits that criminal offending in adulthood and adolescence is determined by behavioral and attitudinal patterns that have been learned during an individual's development such that early years of the life course are most influential in shaping later experiences (Tremblay & Craig 1995). Truancy which is most prevalent and mostly approached by punishment could be counterproductive as it is not what goes on outside the school that contributes to truancy and absenteeism but what takes place in the school. The school should have activities which attract pupils to come to school (Gray *et al.*, 1994). Communities with high levels of truancy have correspondingly high levels of crime (Barker *et al.*, 2001). Tremblay and Craig's (1995) submits that developmental crime prevention is a major strategy in preventing delinquency and later offending which could be corrected through effective developmental prevention programs that is multimodal, meaning that multiple risk factors could be targeted with different interventions and implemented before adolescence.

2.1.4 Lagos State Crime Management Strategies

Establishment of Lagos State Security Trust Fund

The Lagos State Security Trust Fund (LSSTF) established in September 2007 is a direct response to the security challenges in the State which the limited and under equipped federal security agencies of NPF, NSCDC, FRSC cannot surmount. LSSTF was floated to look into ways and means of combating the growing menace of violent crimes as earlier report made it crystal clear that the problem of incapability is centrally related to lack of manpower, logistics, mobility, communications, kitting etc when considering the peculiar security challenges in the state. The Board of Trustees of the Fund, though appointed by the Governor, are mainly (80%) from the private sector and operate independently of government. They are notable members of the business community in the State that use their goodwill to attract donations to the Fund.

The idea of creating a Trust Fund was to source for funds from government, private organizations and individuals in order to meet the operational capacity needs of security agencies particularly in the areas of logistics and provision of crime fighting equipment in the effective discharge of their duties due to long years of neglect by the Federal Government in funding. LSSTF does not receive any subvention from government; rather government makes donations in kind to the Fund. The Fund also ensures that all donations are properly accounted for and that its operations are transparent. In addition, the account of the Trust Fund is audited by International Auditing Firms of Ernst & Young with

a published annual account for public information at the yearly Town Hall Meetings on Security with the Governor where the LSSTF renders its account of stewardship.

- Rapid Response Squad

Rapid Response Squad (RRS) is a section of the Lagos State Police Command set up to respond speedily to emergencies within Lagos State. It was initially referred to as 'Operation Sweep' during the Buba Marwa military administration and later restructured and re-organized and renamed RRS by Tinubu administration. The Squad was charged with onerous task of flushing crime out of every part of Lagos State. The RRS comprises of about two thousand officers. LSSTF donation to equip the RRS to enhance its operational capability and the effectiveness is reflected in the thousands of motorbikes, patrol vehicles, helicopters, gunboats, ballistic helmets/bullet proof vests, rain coats/boots, etc provided for the RRS which has helped to significantly reduce the crime rate in the State. The LSSTF is the "unseen" face behind the RRS.

- Mass Deployment of Closed Circuit Television

A comprehensive security strategy (the safe city project) to enable Central Security Surveillance.

- Mass Deployment of Body Camera Gadgets

This as part of the equipment deployed in tackling the incessant violent attacks on Law Enforcement Officers, while also reducing to the barest minimum cases of misconduct on the part of the Officers.

- Mass Lighting up of City

Improved lighting deters potential offenders by increasing the risk that they will be seen when committing crimes. It also makes law enforcement agents to become more visible, thus leading to a decision to desist from crime. It is a form of target hardening which Lagos State deploy by increasing the levels of illumination on the street or in public spaces. Overall, the evidence suggests that such intervention can reduce crime by an average of 21 per cent in areas with improved street lighting compared to areas without (Adinde, 2019; College of Policing, 2015).

Establishment of Law Enforcement Training Institute

One of the plausible reforms of Lagos state in crime management is the establishment of The Law Enforcement Training Institute, (LETI), P.S.S.D.C. Yard, Magodo, Lagos. Trainings of all the Lagos state paramilitary services are extensively done here with emphasis on civility and basic communal relationship. This training also facilitated officers to be brought to speed on usage of modern equipment which the state is deploying to harden up crime target and reduce opportunity for crime and criminalities such as training on the CCTV, training on body worn camera and training on the Light Up the City concept to displace crime. LETI has capacity to train tens of thousands law enforcement (Ugbodaga, 2021). There is the need for state government to ensure that body of facilitators are drawn from all the federal security agencies as such cosmopolitan outlook of trainers will further cement the foundation for operation synergy

- The Lagos Neighborhood Safety Corps

The Lagos Neighborhood Safety Corps (LNSC) is a uniformed security agency established in 2016 to assist the Police and other security agencies to maintain law and order in all the 57 LGA/LCDA in Lagos. Recruited LNSC officers are locals from where they operate, a policy to make use of their local knowledge to achieve maximum grass root intelligence gathering about crimes, crime in progress, suspicious activities and crime suspects among other things and making available such relevant information to the police or other security agencies that require it, LNSC undertake routine motorized patrol day and night (Ngwu & Ahuruonye, 2017).

The LNSC routine is basically working as community police, they serve as medium between the local community and the Police. The corps by reason of purpose is closer to the people. The officers designated to respective nooks and crannies of all Lagos communities are those who are familiar with almost all the residents of their community. They know the tendencies of almost every individual in the community and are quick to identify new faces once they see them. The LNSC works in synergy with other federal security agencies to carry out wholesale community policing of shift that span 24hours. Some of the challenges faced by the Agency from inception is recognition and acceptability as populace sees them "Olopa Ambode" (Ambode's Policemen) in the misconception that Ambode formed the Agency for confidential reasons. This perception has since changed after a series of crime control records and sensitization.

- New Communication System for Security Agencies

The State created Nigeria's first dedicated emergency call centre to allow security agencies to use a unified communication system and further constrict crime space for operation. Publication of telephone numbers of senior police officers for public usage in case of distress. There is the provision of new police information and complaints boxes at strategic locations all over the state

2.1.5 Salient Crime Triggers in Lagos State

Allied Services for Area Boys

The patronage enjoyed by area boys and miscreants from, Politician, hoteliers and transport union even of Lebanese businessmen who hire area boys as bodyguards of intimidators; while night clubs, restaurants and brothels in several parts of Lagos employ their services as enforcers. Whenever ethnic tension rises, area boys are seen used by disgruntled parties to settle political or business scores, hence there is the need for the State government to evolve a law to deter both the mobilisers and the mobilized area boys

Empowerment of Warlords as Extension of Government

It has gone beyond speculations that the notorious MC Oluomo is an extension of the Lagos state government, if not entire Southwest, leveraging on the National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW). Most palliative measures are duly channeled through him for His "Boys" either the performance of Hajj or Jerusalem pilgrimage and as such the entire transportation networks in Lagos operates on this Warlords networks and shots calling. The revenue that accrues to warlords and the master; MC Oluomo, at the apex of the warlords structure equals the Internally Generated Revenue of some Local government in the country, MC Oluomo is known to be mobilized to spots within Southwest region to settle political scores for their master during, before and after election. All these developments that confers affluence on warlords are predictor to crime and criminalities as most graduates and illiterates see the power wielded by an illiterate while they can hardly eke a decent living from their decent struggles (Nigerian Bulletin, 2020)

Proliferation of Shanty Settlements and Demolition

Proliferation of slums and blight settlement is another major predictor of crime and criminalities and government demolition exercises in Southwest, Nigeria (Maroko, Eleko, Ajah, Makoko) have displaced thousand causing housing insecurity. These unabated demolitions have led to structural disadvantage and social destabilization which have exacerbated homelessness and driven many young people to occupy obscure places making them vulnerable to be recruited into criminal gangs and networks (Dano *et al.* 2019).

Prevalence of Drug Substance

The uncontrolled and unregulated access to hard substance particularly in Lagos, has acted as purveyor that encouraged crime and criminalities such that; alcohol, Methamphetamine, Tramol, Tranabolic steroids, Club drug, Cocaine, Heroin, Inhalant, Burukutu, Marijuana, and narcotic wine are some of the illicit substances that enhances violent crimes; banditry kidnapping, unnecessary violence, and many other imperil atrocities.

Activities of Lagos miscreants known as area boys are strongly associated with the drug trade. No gainsaying that Nigeria has gained notoriety as a major transit centre in the global trade such that Area boys are locked into the drug habit and crime barons are content and desirous to keep them so, to ensure the desperation that makes them conducive to use in organized violence. The addicted drug users are found at hot spots in the day and night jonesing (suffering from withdrawal symptoms, shivering and feeling pain) a condition which can only be relieved by taking another dose of gbana (heroin or cocaine). This drug dependency makes them the foot soldiers for organized street violence. Thus, the solution to the problem of area boys must be taken together with the drug problem.

Unemployment

The apparent inability of the federal government albeit state or local government to provide employment for teeming graduates in this 21st century is geometrically worrisome and all proactive measure engaged by all tiers of government to hold back the unemployment monsters and its menace has failed woefully to the extent that the numbers of unemployed youths continue to increase every day. To this effect, Kilishi *et al.* (2014), believes that the rising trend of crime in Nigeria is usually blamed on the high rate of unemployment. Hence, Suleiman (2017) concludes that the problem of unemployment in Nigeria is one of the major syndromes that upturned youths to become atrocious actors.

Unregulated Street Economic Activities

Lagos State is widely known for street economic activities on both her expressways, highways and arterial roads. It's a trade plied by the poor lower-class residents in search of economic survival. These unwholesome activities on the bridge, under the bridge, around bus stops and garages are often done during traffic congestions. This malady apart from encouraging child abuse also expose the female hawkers to preying rapists while the able body youths are easily recruited by armed robbers and drug traffickers who take advantage of the medium (Akiyode, 2018).

2.2 Empirical Review

2.2.1 Environmental Target Hardening Strategy and Human Security in Lagos, Nigeria

Adegoke (2016) anchored on social contract theory, the study investigated the nexus between deployment of modern security equipment, operation light-up-Lagos and the establishment of the Security Trust Fund in Lagos State, Nigeria. Secondary data method is adopted by making use of Police records, the internet, newspaper and academic journals for data collection. The findings of this paper revealed that the effect of insecurity can hinder sustainable development, loss of lives and properties and even discourage foreign investors. Study only focused on target hardening through provision of security equipment but did not consider stemming crime from cradle through developmental prevention strategy which study considers.

Badiora and Fadoyin (2014) investigated nexus between residents' feeling of safety and crime management strategies in Oshogbo, Nigeria. Study employed survey research design while descriptive analysis and correlation regression was used to present data analysed. Results from study submitted that significant relationship existed between residents' feeling of safety and crime management and prevention strategies observed and that residents of Osogbo, Osun State have a good feeling of safety at home, work place and in public places. Result of study cannot be generalised particularly for a megacity like Lagos hence the need for a similar study using Lagos State

Omotoso and Aderinto (2016) examined the existence of corporate private security organizations and their challenges in crime prevention in Lagos State. The study leveraged on In-depth Interview, structure questionnaire, and Key informant Interview methods administered to 1,200 respondents in gated neighborhoods in four LGAs. Results from study showed that the challenges facing corporate private security organizations included poor training, poor remuneration and welfare schemes owing to the absence of clear operational standards. Study sees activities of private security firms as deterrent to crime but this study employs the development prevention strategy to go beyond target hardening

Ogunsanya (2021) leveraged Institutional theory to investigate the impact of the Lagos Neighbourhood Safety Agency on the security challenges. The study engaged qualitative study approach with purposive sampling strategy for data collection. Analysis from findings revealed that the Lagos State Neighbourhood Safety Agency has not been adequately equipped to combat insecurity in the state due to lack of proper recruitment process, inadequate training of security personnel, misplaced priority of personnel of the agency, and dearth of modern security equipment. The though done in Lagos did not consider developmental protection strategy of crime management which this study does. On a contrast note, the study of Fatile *et al.* (2020), to ascertain the extent to which Neighbourhood Safety Corps is equipped and empowered to provide security to Lagosian. The study which engaged triangulation method correlational analysis on data, submitted that the provision of adequate equipment to community personal enhances the security of lives and properties as the creation of community policing to support the government apparatus reduced the crime rate in any society.

Ojedokun and Ogundipe (2017) engaged qualitative and exploratory research design to investigate the criminal and banditry patterns of motorcycle theft and experiences of victimised commercial motorcyclists in Oyo town. Study was underpinned by routine activity theory. Data was extracted through key-informant interview and focus group discussion methods while snowball sampling technique was utilised for the selection of victims of motorcycle theft. Findings from the study revealed that motorcycle thieves are organized bandits that specialized in snatching motorcycles. The study was conducted on banditry using Oyo State data, there exists the need to extend objective of study to Lagos state, Nigeria

Mbah (2020) empirically examined Lagos home's defence against curfew bandits and the One Million Man March Boys during the Covid-19 lockdown. Findings from the study revealed that quick mobilization of residents into forming of vigilantes averted being overrun by bandits who had earlier ransacked homes, carted away valuables and injured some residents who put up a fight on nearby streets dispossessing residents of their personal belongings. Residents

barricaded entrance into their streets by arming themselves with cutlasses, clubs and all sorts of crude weapons. Study is limited to target hardening while present study perused the need for developmental prevention strategy.

2.2.2 *Developmental Prevention Strategy and Human Security in Lagos, Nigeria*

Agbabiaka (2016) employed systematic sampling procedure to investigate social implications that interplayed during Eyo festival in Lagos Island in Nigeria. Study engaged deployment of questionnaire to elicit data while study was underpinned by system exchange theory. Results of findings revealed that there exist an increase in crime rate and banditry as 98.3% respondents emphasised that there is always increase in crime and social vices whenever it is time for Eyo festival, while only 1.7% have different opinion; an indication that to a large extent crimes and social vices like picking pocket, rape, stealing, smoking of Indian helm among others are prevalent due to the porosity in the nature of *Isaleeko* and the influx of people from different part of the country and beyond. A state specific study on developmental prevention issues but did not consider target hardening which this study considers.

Agi (2017) leveraged on learning theory to examine counseling strategies deployable by parents and government in curbing different deviant behaviours in our educational system. The study was an exploratory research studies with reliance on secondary data, extant literature and related publications on deviant behaviour. The study submitted that the alarming rate of truancy, malpractice, rape, bullying, stealing, truancy, lateness and sexual immorality in educational centres is worrisome and deserves attention. Study did not link these concerning crime developmental issues to the larger society windows which this study does to establish that crime control strategy starts from the cradle vnd vll stakeholder including NGOs should be critical about it.

Nyika and Kurebwa (2014) examined employable strategies by primary school teachers in Sadza, cluster in managing truancy in primary schools in Zimbabwe. The study deployed structured interviews and randomly administered questionnaires on sampled teachers. Findings from the study established that truancy was rampant in Sadza cluster. Some of the strategies used were collaborative and dialogical solutions to the problems, teacher-parent consultations and providing a motivating curriculum. The study submitted the peer group and the community at large should be included in truancy management programmes. The study though done in Zimbabwe, result of which cannot be generalised for a Nigeria study.

Ndidibuike and Nwadiuso (2018) deployed triangulation research design to investigate strategies for curbing deviant behaviors among secondary school students. The study employed a descriptive survey approach and random sampling technique on 972 teachers in Udi Local Government Area of Enugu State. Findings from analysis submitted that drug abuse, examination malpractice and truancy are forms of deviant behaviors found among secondary school students. Study did not involve contribution of government and NGOs in stemming the tide of which this study will do since developmental prevention is concerned about such.

2.3 **Theoretical Framework**

2.3.1 *Participatory Theory*

Participation has theory posits that a meaningful social change in any development initiative cannot be achieved only by external experts involving in development processes irrespective of whether development is taking place in developed or developing countries (World Bank, 1996). Ramaswamy (2004) argued that if individuals have an opportunity to directly participate in decision making at the local level, they can achieve real control over the course of their everyday life. Participatory theory is based on principles which can be found in the context of community policing; solutions to contemporary community problems demand freeing both people and the police to explore ways to address neighborhood concerns, decentralization of powers to ensure participation of people in the formulation of policies from bottom to top, it also ensures greater police accountability to the public (Adam & Andre, 2016).

Despite the ambitious direction in which participatory approach strengthen community's and citizens participation in development processes, the approach still faces operational challenges even there is presently pocketful of altercations between federal security agencies (NPF, NSCDC, FRSC and members of the Community Oriented Policing; LNSC, LASMA, the overlapping of crimes from neighbourhood back to the highway without the federal agencies arresting the situation for example "a potential pitfall of joint decision-making in a group of stakeholders representing diverse social positions and technical backgrounds is the power imbalance among actors that threatens the integrity of a participatory strategy" (Inagaki 2007). Despite the approach potential shortcomings there is ample evidence that participatory concept has gained acceptance in the mainstream status in community policing (Thomas, 1994).

3. Methodology

This study employs exploratory research design to examine megacity crime management strategies on human security, using target hardening and developmental prevention strategies in Lagos state, Nigeria. Human security is assessed with safety of lives and properties. The study relies solely on secondary data. The research is conducted by examining literature concerning the crime management strategies in megacity to curtail violent crimes. The literature was obtained through searches in publicly available material. Literature from non-serial publications, official reports, and conferences has been included particularly if they have been cited by other references in term of crime management and human security.

4. Discussion

The review of literature reveals that environmental target hardening in Lagos state has positive effects on human security. The rationale for this finding could be that installation of CCTV, Light-Up-the-City scheme, deployment of LNSC officers into nooks and crannies of Lagos negatively impacted on ability of criminal to perpetuate crimes, thus increasing the cost of crime. The finding is in tandem with the findings in the previous works of Adegoke (2016); Badiora and Fadoyin (2014); Omotoso and Aderinto (2016) Ogunsanya (2021); Ojedokun and Ogundipe (2017); Mbah (2020) who found that deployment of LNSC into neighbourhood, private security companies and vigilante engagement helps to stem crime which threatens human security.

The result gotten from scanty empirical literature is that there is a near total absence of government and NGOS involvement in evolving developmental protection strategy which involves curbing abnormal criminal behaviour from cradle particularly from the educational sectors where acts that blossom in later life to crime are variously exhibited. The rationale could be that Government believe parents and schools are capable enough to control deviance at tender stage. This finding is consistent with the findings in the previous work of Agbabiaka (2016); Agi (2017); Ndidibuike and Nwadiuso (2018); Nyika and Kurebwa (2014).

5. Conclusion

The study concludes that target hardening should be sustained in Lagos while federal security agencies that are into macro policing of major highways should be seen doing their jobs as traffic banditry and other violent crimes are on the rise. More collaborative efforts between LNSC, LASMA and other federal security agencies should be further encouraged.

The study equally concludes that government should take developmental protection strategy very serious by being involved in control of deviance trait from the cradle in the educational sector, encouraging NGOs to be involved and declaring a zero tolerance war on drugs cartel as majority of criminals are deeply into drugs.

Based on the conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are made;

- The study recommends that Lagos state government should invest more into target hardening towards achieving a safer city with a sustainability plan for such capital security investment drive, while the Federal Government should also give a support as a safer Lagos translates to confidence of foreign investors in the country.
 - In light of the findings of the study, the study also recommends that Lagos state government apart from being seen involved, the government should engage more NGOs in evolving a stronger developmental protection strategy, to root out early traits of deviance in the educational sectors at all levels, such deviance control mechanism should be deeply inculcated in both formal and informal educational system in order to stem traces of crime and criminalities at tender ages.
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Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

Deep appreciation goes to Prof Zamani Andrew for his sterling contributions to the success of this work.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest.

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